

Financing as a Determinant of Quality Administration for Vocational Education Graduates' Output

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Abstract

The paper examined financing as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education graduates' output. The population of the study consist of 250 Vocational Education Lecturers. Four research questions and four research hypotheses were formulated for the study. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire named "Financing Administration Questionnaire (FDQAQ)" with 25 items. A test-retest reliability technique was adopted to ascertain the degree of internal consistency. A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient of 0.87 confirmed that the instrument was reliable for data collection. A total number of 250 copies of the instrument was administered and all were duly completed and retrieved. Data collected were analyzed using the mean score(x) and standard deviation (SD), while inferential statistics were used to test the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, among others, that financing is highly linked to the quality of vocational education graduates' output because it provides the resources required based on the concept of input and output. The study recommended that financing is needed for capacity building and carrying capacity if quality vocational education is to be achieved and sustained.

Keywords: Financing, graduates, quality administration, vocational, vocational education.

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Introduction

Education is an expensive social service and requires adequate financial provision from all tiers of government, non-governmental organizations, companies and general programmes (Offem & Ononiwu, 2020). The Nigerian education system consists of primary, secondary and tertiary levels. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) stated clearly, the need for functional education that has to be relevant and practical for the acquisition of appropriate skills and development of competencies as equipment for individuals to live in and contribute to the development of the country. According to Offem (2015) opined that for a nation to progress and witness development, she must give the right values and education that can develop the youths into sound and effective citizens and fully integrate them into the community.

Pre-technical and vocational education are aimed at imparting vocational skills, commercial and economic development, necessary for self-reliance and fulfilling some of the goals of Technical and Vocational Education. Similarly, it prepares students for a higher-order study as Business Education in the constituent subjects requiring that minimum standards and/or competencies and skills be attained by the students. Therefore, the goal and objectives of vocational-technical education can only be achieved through proper financing. Onejetah (2011) maintained that funding deals with financing, whereby provision is made for every sphere of human endeavour (including education), that is based on the concepts of input and output. Funding is regarded as the act of providing money or financial resources for a particular purpose continuously. Such money or financial resources should be enough to cater for the project or programme for which they are provided (Hornby in Olufunwa, Waziri & Olorunmolu, 2013). Funding entails the financial activities of authorities in terms of taxing, spending, borrowing and lending and it involves the means of providing for the expenditure involved in the staffing, equipment and maintenance of institutions (Onye & Anyaogu, 2018).

According to Nwakudu (2014), funding is the management of large amounts of money by governments or large organizations, especially public money. This definition presupposes that for programmes planned to be executed, funds must be sourced and made available. Furthermore, fundings refer to the process of sourcing, allocating and managing public school revenues in the production of educational services for the attainment of educational objectives. In the opinion of Ogbonnaya (2012) funding has three different definitions of funding: it refers to the Science of controlling money and not the real money itself; it involves not only the raising of funds to achieve organizational goals but also involves the allocation and prudent management of such funds; it involves supervision of receipts and payments of money to an organization or institution for a project or program run by the school. Idiahe (2011) maintain that school finding could be defined as available funds set aside for achieving the objectives of a particular project. It is very important to have an enabling resource in the day-to-day running of educational institutions. Its provision or lack determines the success or failure of educational programmes.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to examine financing as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education graduates' output. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the perception of vocational education lecturers on funding as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education programmes.
2. determine the types of infrastructural facilities needed for quality vocational education programmes management
3. quantify the extent of qualified lecturers needed in vocational education programmes
4. Determine the conformity of course outline in a vocational education programme.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study

1. To what extent does funding serve as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education?
2. What types of infrastructural facilities are needed for vocational education programmes management?
3. To what extent are qualified lecturers needed for a vocational educational programme?
4. To what extent is the conformity of course outline in enhancing vocational education graduates' production?

Statement of hypothesis

The hypothesis formulated to direct the study is that:

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on funding as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education graduates' output.

Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was all lecturers in the Department of Vocational Education across the four higher institutions that offer vocational education in Cross River State with a total of 245 respondents. There was no sampling in this study due to the small population size. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire which consists of two parts. Part 'A' collected personal data and part 'B' elicited responses on the questionnaire items. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA = 4 points); Agree (A = 3 points); Disagree (D = 2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1 point). The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by two experts from the University of Calabar. A reliability test was conducted using the test-retest approach. Data collected from both sets of administrations were subjected to a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis that yielded a coefficient of 0.87 that was considered accurate for the study. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the data gathered. Any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above was regarded as strongly agreed and anyone below it was regarded as disagreed. The z-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level. The value is significant where the calculated z-value was greater than the critical z-table value. In which case, the null hypothesis will be rejected; the hypothesis will, however, be accepted where the calculated value is less than the critical table value.

Results

Research questions 1

To what extent does funding serve as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education? The result in Table 1 was used to answer this research question. The result showed that male and female respondents held similar views on the extent funding is important for the administration of vocational education. Going by the results in Table 1, it can be inferred that there is a high degree of acceptance among respondents on the role funding plays in enhancing effective administration of vocational education in universities for quality graduates' production.

Table 1: Mean rating with standard deviation of male and female respondents' views on the extent of funding as a determinant of quality administration for vocational education

S/ N	Items	Male		Deci sion	Female		Decisi on
		\bar{x}	SD		\bar{x}	SD	
1.	Financing can be used to access the performance of graduates.	2.90	0.87	Acce pted	2.88	0.96	Accept ed
2.	The use of appropriate strategies for teaching vocational education can be achieved through effective financing.	2.83	0.66	Acce pted	2.87	0.88	Accept ed
3.	Capacity building for quality vocational education requires adequate financing.	2.94	0.87	Acce pted	2.73	0.95	Accept ed
4.	Adequate financing improves the capacity of vocational education graduates.	3.18	0.64	Acce pted	2.93	0.96	Accept ed
5.	Sufficient financing of vocational education required ICT skills for quality.	3.86	0.79	Acce pted	2.93	0.87	Accept ed
6.	Vocational Education lecturers should be motivated through payment of the allowance.	2.86	0.76	Acce pted	2.76	0.92	Accept ed
7.	The entitlement of vocational education lecturers should be paid promptly to boost the quality	2.24	0.90	Unac cepte d	2.76	0.92	Unacce pted
8.	Sufficient financing should be provided to facilitate quality	2.36	0.82	Unac cepte d	2.47	0.96	Unacce pted
9.	The financing level enable stakeholders to access quality mechanism of vocational education delivery	2.89	0.74	Acce pted	2.82	1.00	Accept ed
10	Financing is the most important determinant of any educational programme	3.05	0.90	Acce pted	2.82	0.94	Accept ed
11	The result of a quality investigation of vocational education should be directly linked to adequate financing	3.11	1.37	Acce pted	2.82	0.94	Accept ed
12	Linking the quality of vocational education to financing is necessary for effective accountability	2.89	0.87	Acce pted	2.76	0.92	Accept ed

13	Linking the quality of vocational education to financing will not produce an incentive for improvement.	2.47	0.93	Unaccepted	2.46	0.92	Unaccepted
14	Linking quality research in vocational education to financing enhance quality output	2.86	0.96	Accepted	2.75	0.94	Accepted

Research question 2

What types of infrastructural facilities are needed for vocational education programmes management? The result of the analysis in table 2 indicated that all items on infrastructural facilities are score above the mean. This revealed that infrastructural facilities will be needed in teaching vocational education.

Table 2: Mean rating of Vocational Education Lecturers on infrastructural facilities needed

S/N	Variables	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Green low for practical teaching	3.0	1.22	SA
2.	Teaching with ICT	3.10	1.01	SA
3.	Teaching with lecture note	3.20	1.10	SA

Research question 3

To what extent are qualified lecturers be needed in vocational education programmes? The result of the data analysis in tables showed that all the items were rated above the mean. This implies that qualified lecturers are needed in vocational education.

Table 3: Mean rating response of qualified lecturers needed in a vocational education programme

S/N	Qualified Lecturers	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Qualified lecturers help to produce quality graduates in vocational education	3.02	0.90	SA
2.	Unqualified lecturers hamper the production of quality graduates	3.05	0.89	SA
3.	Qualified lecturers always covered their course outline	3.10	0.76	SA

Research question 4

To what extent does vocational education course outline conform with the needed quality? In table 4; the analysis indicated that all the items are needed to a high extent. This means that these items are needed for the production of quality vocational education graduates.

Table 4: Mean rating responses of lecturers teaching vocational education programmes on the need of course outline conformity on vocational education

S/N	Conformity of Course outline of Vocational Education	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Course outline – Conformity – will help to produce quality vocational education graduates	3.10	.89	SA
2.	Course outline conformity will make vocational educational graduates not to be qualify	3.20	1.02	SA
3.	Course outline conformity will help lecturers to lecture vocational education content to qualify/standard	3.01	.83	SA

Discussion

The finding in table 1 data analysis revealed that all the items were accepted or agreed upon as funding determinants that enhance the effective quality of vocational education graduates' output for societal development. This study corresponds to Kulo-et al in Offem and Ononiwu (2020) who stated that in the wake of the global economic recession and mass youth unemployment, whose impacts are more pronounced in developing economies, the need for vocational and technical education is increasingly apparent as is the need for adequate funding.

Conclusion

Based on the study, it was concluded that funds should be made available by the government, for the effective development of any educational system/programme. In other words, the fund is necessary for the provision of infrastructures, employment, re-training and payment of staff salaries, provision of materials and equipment and for the conduct of researches. Therefore, finance can make or mar the realization of any educational programmes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made;

1. Sufficient funds should be made available for purchasing learning facilities most especially in practical courses as a vocational-technical education programme.
2. There should be a regular staff development programme to give life to the programme to enable it attained its goals.
3. Funding of education generally should not be left in the hands of government alone; rather it should be a joint force by the government, stakeholders, non-governmental organizations, parents and individuals.
4. There should be frequent monitor/supervision of fund allocation to education for effective utilization.

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